

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

EFFECT OF PLANT GROWTH REGULATORS AND FERTILIZERS ON THE VEGETATIVE GROWTH OF SUNFLOWER (*HELIANTHUS ANNUUS* L.)

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Abstract

The effect of synthetic plant growth regulators Methyur, Kamethur and Ivin, as well as fertilizers Rostok Extra and Radix Tim forte plus, used separately or together, on the growth of four-week-old sunflower (*Helianthus annuus* L.) variety Azimuth was studied. Synthetic plant growth regulators Methyur and Kamethur, as well as fertilizers Rostok extra and Radix Tim forte plus, when used separately or together, had the greatest stimulating effect on the growth of sunflower shoots and roots. Synthetic plant growth regulator Ivin showed the highest effect on the growth of sunflower shoots and roots when used in combination with fertilizers Rostok extra and Radix Tim forte plus. The results obtained confirmed the prospect for the practical application of plant growth regulators Methyur, Kamethur and Ivin, used separately or in combination with fertilizers Rostok Extra and Radix Tim forte plus, to improve the growth and development of sunflower (*Helianthus annuus* L.) variety Azimuth in the vegetative phase.

Keywords: sunflower, plant growth regulators, fertilizers.

Introduction. Sunflower (*Helianthus annuus* L) belongs to the Asteraceae (Compositae) family of the genus *Helianthus*, numbering more than 60 species [1, 2]. Sunflower (*Helianthus annuus* L) is the fourth most important oilseed in the world, used primarily for seed oil production [1, 2]. Sunflower seeds contain about 44% oil and 16% proteins [2]. Sunflower oil accounts for 9.2% of the world production of vegetable oils, after palm (36.5%), soybean (27.4%) and rapeseed (12.5%) oils [2].

Sunflower oil is enriched with polyunsaturated fatty acids, important for human nutrition, such as oleic acid (monounsaturated omega-9) – 30%, linoleic acid (polyunsaturated omega-6) – 59%, as well as a low content of saturated fatty acids such as palmitic acid – 5%, and stearic acid - 6% [3]. Sunflower seeds, stem, leaf and roots are enriched with mineral elements and phytochemicals (dietary fiber, manganese, vitamins, steroids, triterpene glycosides, glutathione reductase, flavonoids, phenolic acids, carotenoids, chlorogenic acid, caffeic acid, alkaloids, tannins, saponins, amino acids, fruits acids), due to which they are used to prepare extracts with antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, antipyretic, antitumor, anti-cardiovascular, anti-asthmatic, laxative, diuretic, expectorant, antidiabetic, anthelmintic and antioxidant properties for the treatment of various diseases, as well as for the preparation of sunflower meal for food and feed supplements [3 – 12].

The harvested area under this crop worldwide is about 25 million hectares, of which an average 36 million tons of seeds are produced. During 2014–2018, harvested sunflower areas in such countries as Ukraine, Russia, Argentina, China, Romania, Bulgaria, Turkey, Hungary, France and the USA increased to 76% and the production of seeds - to 84% [2]. In 2022, the top 10

countries: India, Russia, Spain, Argentina, France, Ukraine, Hungary, Germany, South Africa, Iran were the main markets in the sunflower oil industry [13]. In the EU countries, the largest producers of sunflower seeds are France with an annual production of about 1.6 million tons and Slovakia with an annual production of about 0.2 million tons of sunflower seeds [14]. Among the countries of South Asia, India is the largest sunflower producer. According to the Ministry of Agriculture of India, for 2019-2020, the total sown area under this crop in India is about 0.48 million hectares, with a total annual production of 0.32 million tonnes and a seed yield of 720 kg/ha [15].

The main factors affecting the growth rate of sunflower, the quantity and quality of oilseed crops are climatic factors, the geographical location of its cultivation areas and soil composition, the use of growth regulators and fertilizers to increase seed yield and oil content in sunflower seeds, as well as means of protection against pathogens and pests [14 - 24].

The creation of new environmentally friendly sunflower growth regulators to improve the growth and increase the yield of this crop is an urgent task for modern agricultural biotechnology. The most promising for solving this problem are synthetic low molecular weight heterocyclic compounds, derivatives of pyridine and pyrimidine, which are currently used as plant growth regulators, herbicides and fungicides [25 - 29].

Previously published works have confirmed the prospects of creating new plant growth regulators based on synthetic low molecular weight heterocyclic compounds, pyridine and pyrimidine derivatives [30 – 40]. The most studied representatives of these classes of synthetic compounds are plant growth regulators: Ivin (N-oxide-2,6-dimethylpyridine), Methyur (sodium salt

of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine), Kamethur (potassium salt of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine), developed at the V.P. Kukhar Institute of Bioorganic Chemistry and Petrochemistry of National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine [31]. These chemical compounds, used in concentrations from 10^{-5} M to 10^{-8} M, exhibit growth-regulating activity similar to phytohormones auxins and cytokinins on various agricultural, industrial and ornamental crops [33, 34, 37 - 42].

Based on the data of previous studies, the aim of this work is to study the effect of synthetic plant growth regulators Methyur, Kamethur and Ivin, used separately or in combination with fertilizers Rostok Extra and Radix Tim forte plus, on the growth of sunflower

(*Helianthus annuus* L.) variety Azimuth in the vegetative phase.

Materials and methods. In laboratory conditions, the regulatory effect of Methyur, Kamethur and Ivin, used separately or in combination with fertilizers Rostok Extra and Radix Tim forte plus, on the growth of sunflower (*Helianthus annuus* L.) variety Azimuth in the vegetative phase was studied.

The chemical structure of the investigated synthetic plant growth regulators Methyur (sodium salt of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine), Kamethur (potassium salt of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine) and Ivin (N-oxide-2,6-dimethylpyridine) is shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Chemical structure and relative molecular mass of synthetic plant growth regulators Methyur, Kamethur and Ivin

The compositions of fertilizer Rostok Extra produced by the LLC "Ukrainian Agrarian Resource" company and fertilizer Radix Tim forte plus produced by the "Forcrop" Company (Spain) are described in detail in the work [39].

Before treatment, sunflower seeds were sterilized with 1% KMnO_4 solution for 3 min, then treated with 96% ethanol solution for 1 min, and then washed three times with sterile distilled water. In control samples, sunflower seeds were treated with distilled water, in experimental samples, sunflower seeds were treated with water solutions of either fertilizer Rostok Extra in a concentration of 100 ml per 1 liter of distilled water or fertilizer Radix Tim forte plus in a concentration of 50 ml per 1 liter of distilled water, or each of the synthetic plant growth regulators: Methyur, or Kamethur, or Ivin in a concentration of 10^{-7} M per 1 liter of distilled water, or a combination of each of the synthetic plant growth regulators Methyur, or Kamethur, or Ivin with the fertilizers Rostok Extra and Radix Tim forte plus used in the above concentrations. After this procedure, the treated seeds were placed in cuvettes (15 - 20 seeds each), supplemented with perlite, and incubated in a thermostat in the dark at a temperature of 22-24°C for 48 hours. Then cuvettes with seeds were placed in a climatic chamber, where sunflower plants were grown for four weeks in a light/dark regime of 16/8 hours, at a temperature of 22-24°C, a light intensity of 3000 lux and an air humidity of 60-80 %. Growth parameters of four-week-old sunflower plants (average length of shoots and roots (cm)) were measured according to the method [43].

Statistical processing of the data of experiments performed in three replications was carried out according to the Student's-t variance test with a significance

level of $P \leq 0.05$; the values are means \pm Standard Deviation (\pm SD) [44].

Results and Discussion. Data from previous studies on synthetic plant growth regulators Methyur, Kamethur and Ivin, carried out in laboratory and field conditions, confirm their high stimulating effect on growth and development of economically important agricultural, industrial and ornamental crops (corn, barley, oats, sorghum, chickpea, sunflower, miscanthus, rose), increasing their productivity, as well as their adaptation to abiotic and biotic stress factors [34, 37 - 42]. These studies also showed that the activity of synthetic plant growth regulators Methyur, Kamethur and Ivin was similar to or higher than that of the phytohormones auxins and cytokinins.

The results of previous studies have shown that synthetic plant growth regulators Methyur, Kamethur and Ivin, as well as the fertilizers Rostok Extra and Radix Tim forte plus, which were used separately or together, have a positive effect on the growth and development of shoots and roots of winter wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) variety Shestopalivka in the vegetative phase [39].

A very promising issue is the study of the effect of synthetic plant growth regulators Methyur, Kamethur and Ivin, used separately or in combination with fertilizers Rostok Extra and Radix Tim forte plus, on the growth and development of an important oilseed crop sunflower (*Helianthus annuus* L.) variety Azimuth in the vegetative phase.

The conducted studies showed that all synthetic plant growth regulators Methyur, Kamethur, Ivin, as well as fertilizers Rostok extra and Radix Tim forte plus, when used separately or together, have a positive effect on the growth of sunflower (*Helianthus annuus* L.) variety Azimuth for 4 weeks (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Effect of plant growth regulators *Methyur*, *Kamethur* and *Ivin* (concentration of $10^{-7}M$), and fertilizers *Rostok extra* (concentration of 100 ml per 1 liter of distilled water) and *Radix Tim forte plus* (concentration of 50 ml per 1 liter of distilled water), used separately or together, on the growth and development of four-week-old sunflower (*Helianthus annuus L.*) variety *Azimuth* compared to control plants

It should be noted that the highest stimulating effect on the growth of shoots and roots of sunflower was shown by synthetic plant growth regulators *Methyur* and *Kamethur*, as well as fertilizers *Rostok extra* and *Radix Tim forte plus* when used separately or in combination: *Methyur*+*Radix Tim forte plus*, *Kamethur*+*Rostok extra*, *Kamethur*+*Radix Tim forte plus*, compared to control plants (Fig. 2).

Synthetic plant growth regulator *Ivin* showed the highest effect on the growth of sunflower shoots and roots when used in combination with fertilizers: *Ivin*+*Rostok extra*, *Ivin*+*Radix Tim forte plus*, compared to control plants (Fig. 2).

The increase in the average shoot length (cm) of sunflower plants occurred both with the separate application of fertilizers: *Rostok extra* - by 96.33%, *Radix Tim forte plus* - by 30.73% and synthetic plant growth regulators: *Ivin* - by 35.89%, *Methyur* - by 88.99%, *Kamethur* - by 30.73%, as well as with the complex application of synthetic plant growth regulators with fertilizers: *Ivin*+*Radix Tim forte plus* - by 45.64%, *Methyur*+*Radix Tim forte plus* - by 44.51%, *Methyur*+*Rostok extra* - by 63.61%, *Kamethur*+*Radix Tim forte plus* - by 125.69%, *Kamethur*+*Rostok extra* - by 107.34%, respectively, compared to the control plants (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Effect of plant growth regulators Methyur, Kamethur and Ivin (concentration of $10^{-7}M$), and fertilizers Rostok extra (concentration of 100 ml per 1 liter of distilled water) and Radix Tim forte plus (concentration of 50 ml per 1 liter of distilled water), used separately or together, on the average shoot length (cm) of four-week-old sunflower (*Helianthus annuus L.*) variety Azimuth compared to control plants. Note. **Significant differences from control values*, $p \leq 0.05$, $n=3$, the values are mean \pm SD

The increase in the average root length (cm) of sunflower plants occurred both with the separate application of fertilizers: Rostok extra - by 13.51%, Radix Tim forte plus - by 81.62%, and synthetic plant growth regulators: Ivin - by 38.38%, Methyur - by 60%, Kamethur - by 100.77%, as well as with the complex ap-

plication of synthetic plant growth regulators with fertilizers: Ivin+Radix Tim forte plus - by 81.08%, Ivin+Rostok extra - by 87.03%, Methyur+Radix Tim forte plus - by 82.24%, Methyur+Rostok extra - by 49.55%, Kamethur+Radix Tim forte plus - by 49.55%, Kamethur+Rostok extra - by 20.27%, respectively, compared to the control plants (Fig. 4).

Figure 4. Effect of plant growth regulators Methyur, Kamethur and Ivin (concentration of $10^{-7}M$), and fertilizers Rostok extra (concentration of 100 ml per 1 liter of distilled water) and Radix Tim forte plus (concentration of 50 ml per 1 liter of distilled water), used separately or together, on the average root length (cm) of four-week-old sunflower (*Helianthus annuus L.*) variety Azimuth compared to control plants. Note. **Significant differences from control values*, $p \leq 0.05$, $n=3$, the values are mean \pm SD

Summarizing the data obtained, it should be noted that the effect of the synthetic plant growth regulators Methyur, Kamethur and Ivin, when used separately or in combination with fertilizers Rostok extra and Radix Tim forte plus, on plant growth is similar to the regulatory effect of phytohormones auxins and cytokinins that control the elongation, division and differentiation of plant cells, the formation and growth of plant tissues and organs [35, 45 – 48].

In addition, the plant growth regulator Kamethur contains the macronutrients nitrogen, potassium and sulfur, and plant growth regulator Ivin contains the macronutrient nitrogen required for sunflower growth and metabolism, while plant growth regulator Methyur contains the macronutrients nitrogen and sulfur, as well as the chemical element sodium, which play an important role in plant adaptation to salt and osmotic stress [31, 34, 49 – 51]. Macronutrients and micronutrients present in fertilizers, such as nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, magnesium, sulfur, manganese, boron, zinc, iron, copper, as well as free amino acids and humic substances, improve plant growth and metabolism [39].

Similar results have been obtained in previous studies on the effect of plant growth regulators Ivin, Methyur and Kamethur on sunflower growth and productivity [41]. It was shown that pre-sowing treatment of seeds with water solutions of Ivin, Methyur and Kamethur at a concentration of $10^{-7}M$ contributes to an increase in morphological parameters (length of shoot and root, fresh weight of plant and basket) and biochemical parameters (content of chlorophylls a and b, and carotenoids) of sunflower (*Helianthus annuus* L.) variety Bastion grown in field conditions for 3 months.

The data obtained in previous work [41] and in the present work indicate the prospect of practical application of plant growth regulators Methyur, Kamethur and Ivin, used separately or in combination with fertilizers Rostok Extra and Radix Tim forte plus to improve vegetative growth and increase sunflower yields.

Conclusion. Thus, the obtained results indicate the possibility of using the plant growth regulators Methyur, Kamethur and Ivin separately or in combination with fertilizers Rostok extra and Radix Tim forte plus, for the pre-sowing treatment of sunflower (*Helianthus annuus* L.) seeds variety Azimuth to increase the length of shoots and roots in the vegetative phase.

Conflict of interest. The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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